

Quorum Sensing (QS) As Etiological Phenomenon: The Bacterial Paradigm

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Abstract:

Signaling mechanisms that govern physiological and morphological responses to change the cell density are common in bacteria. Quorum sensing is signal transduction processes which involves the production and release of and response to hormone-like molecules (auto-inducers) that accumulate in the external environment as the cell population grows. Quorum sensing is found in a wide variety of bacteria, both Gram-positive and Gram-negative and the spectrum of physiological functions that can be regulated is impressive. Variation in the nature of the extra-cellular signal in the signal detection machinery and in the mechanisms of signal transmission demonstrates the evolutionary adaptability of quorum sensing systems for multiple uses.

Key Words: Quorum sensing, Acyl-homoserine lactone (AHL), Peptides, Auto-induction

Introduction:

The discovery that bacteria are able to communicate with each other changed our general perception of many single, simple organisms in our world. Understanding how bacterial cells communicate with each other has a number of important practical implications for the control of pathogen organisms, and for the screening and exploitation of bacteria that produce antibiotics and other high value products.

Bacteria can assess their local population densities using low molecular-weight molecules (auto inducers) and alter gene expression at high cell number to behave as a group. This process, termed quorum sensing, is widely used by bacteria to initiate group behaviours that have direct and often devastating impact on human health (Bassler & Losick, 2006). Numerous bacterial pathogens use quorum sensing to initiate infection (de Kievit & Iglewski, 2000; Hall-Stoodley et al, 2004). Because these important processes are controlled by chemical signals, there is intense and growing interest in the development of non-native ligands that can intercept these signals and attenuate or mimic quorum sensing outcomes (Lyon & Muir, 2003).

Several classes of microbially derived signalling molecules have now been identified. Broadly, these can be divided into two main categories (i) amino acids and short peptide derivatives, commonly utilized by Gram-

positive bacteria (Lazazzera & Grossman, 1998), and (ii) fatty acid derivatives, called homoserine lactones (HSLs) frequently utilized by Gram-negative bacteria (Whitehead et al, 2001). Whatever may be the nature of the signal molecule, the whole network functions by its re-entry into the cell either via diffusion or by an active transport. The signalling mechanism involves subsequent interaction of the signal with an intracellular effector that will induce the pathway for the concerned phenotype (Fig.I)

Fig. I: A sequential pathway for biofilm formation via quorum sensing in bacterium *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Gram-positive bacteria:

Most of the signaling systems found in Gram-positive bacteria use oligopeptides as signals that are detected by two-component phosphorelay proteins (Dunny & Leonard, 1997). In many cases, the receptor is a membrane spanning histidine kinase, while in other systems the receptor is a cytoplasmic phosphatase that dephosphorylates a response regulator. A third type of peptide receptor, found in *Enterococcus faecalis*, is a transcriptional repressor (Shi et al, 2005). However, in contrast to the common use of peptide signals, one group of Gram-positive bacteria, the Actinomycetes, uses butyrolactone signals to regulate the production of antibiotics and other secondary metabolites (Natsume

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et al, 2004). Several peptide-dependent signaling systems in Gram-positive organisms have been intensively studied. For example, the Accessory curve regulator (*agr* BDCA) locus of *Staphylococcus aureus* regulates a battery of pathogenic genes via a peptide derived from *agr* D. *agr* D is processed and exported by *agr* B, and detected by the *agr* A/*agr* C two-component system (Lyon & Novick, 2004; fig.IIA)). *agr* D is synthesized as a 45-amino-acid precursor, which is processed to an eight residue mature form containing a thio-lactone ring. Extra-cellular peptides bind to *agr* C, triggering phosphorylation of *agr* A, which activates expression of a gene encoding a non coding RNA that, in turn, regulates a large number of pathogenesis determinants.

Gram-negative eubacteria:

Proteobacteria generally signal via Acyl-homoserine lactones (AHLs), the archetypical quorum-sensing molecules, were first discovered in *Vibrio fischeri*. Acyl homoserine lactone are synthesized from S-adenosyl-L-methionine (SAM) and acylated acyl carrier protein (acyl-ACP; More et al, 1996). The acyl

chain length can vary from 4 to 18 carbons and can also vary in oxidation state and degree of desaturation (Fuqua et al, 1994). Most AHLs are made by proteins that resembles the LuxI protein of *V. fischeri*, and are detected by AHL dependent transcription factors that resemble the *Vibrio fischeri* LuxR protein. *V. fischeri* colonizes the light organs of various species of fish or marine invertebrates. As the population of cells grow within the light organ of *Vibrio fischeri* the concentration of external AHL increases. When the autoinducer concentration reaches the micromolar range, its efflux from the cells becomes balanced by an influx, so that it can interact with LuxR. LuxR autoinducer complexes bind the luciferase promoter and activate transcription (Fig. II B).

Quorum Sensing Regulation in Bacteria:

Quorum Sensing regulation involves the exchange of small signal molecules like AHLs between nearby bacterial cells. As the local population of bacteria increases, so does the number of signal-producing cells and the signal concentration. Operationally, a “quorum” of bacteria is present when the population density (the signal concentration) reaches levels capable of triggering changes in the gene expression. Quorum sensing regulation is particularly important for the ability of pathogenic bacteria to successfully infect animal hosts, allowing them to remain “stealthy” until the local population is big enough to overwhelm host defences. Mutants with defective quorum sensing are usually avirulent or have significantly reduced virulence. Quorum sensing is similarly important to bacterial symbionts of both plant and animal hosts. The basic molecular mechanics of quorum sensing regulation are fairly simple. For AHLs, there are just two basic protein components: AHL synthase and AHL receptor.

Functions of quorum sensing:

For many organisms of interest within biotechnology, the role of quorum sensing is complicated and unobvious. Indeed, research aimed at elucidating quorum functionality has perhaps left more questions than answers as to how these systems can best be put to use. Views by Cvitkovitch et al, 2003; Greenberg, 2003; Yarwood & Schlievert, 2003 were published as part of series on quorum sensing that described advances made in understanding quorum sensing as it relates to infectious disease. Quorum

Fig. II: Two mechanisms of cell to cell signaling in bacteria. (A) Signaling via peptides by the pathogen *S. aureus* (Lyon & Novick, 2004), (B) Signaling via acylhomoserine lactones by the marine bioluminescent bacterium *Vibrio fischeri* (Fuqua et al, 1994)

sensing is believed to regulate competence development, sporulation, antibiotic synthesis, virulence factor induction, cell differentiation, and nutrient flux along with other physiological events in pathogenic bacterial infections. More recently, quorum-sensing was linked through proteomic analysis to increased pathogenic competence in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Arevalo-Ferro et al, 2004).

Applications:

Pathogen management comprises most of the current applications of quorum-sensing technology. Inhibition of quorum signalling is the most obvious and, in practice, most ubiquitous application of quorum-sensing knowledge. The topic of targeting quorum sensing for the treatment of bacterial infections has been reviewed several times (Stephenson & Hoch, 2004; Hentzer et al, 2003; Hentzer & Givskov, 2003; Lyon & Muir, 2003). The limiting factor for many applications is delivery of a quorum functional (either stimulating or repressing) compound to the organism to be controlled. Staphylococcal subspecies, such as methicillin-resistant *S. aureus*, remain one of the most opportunistic pathogen found in hospital settings. Work published by Balaban et al (2003 a,b) capitalized on quorum sensing to inhibit the development of biofilm by *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*. Both strains were susceptible to an RNA III inhibiting peptide (RIP), a specific inhibitor of quorum sensing that interferes with the gene locus *agr*, which is responsible for staphylococcal toxicity. Expanding this approach to include antibiotics, Balaban et al (2003 a) determined the effect of combining RIP with seven different combinations of antibiotics and found that in every case the combination of RIP and an antibiotic greatly improved the performance of the antibiotic.

Looking to Gram-negative bacterial infections, characterization of *P. aeruginosa* from patients revealed quorum-signalling targets that could be potentially inhibited to prevent the formation of biofilms (Denervaud et al, 2004). Most of the quorum genes expressed were classified as transcription factors. In other work, high concentrations of AI-2 were detected in sputum from patients of cystic fibrosis (Duan et al, 2003). These researchers found that *P. aeruginosa* transcriptional virulence factors could be stimulated by oral pharyngeal microflora and that high concentrations of AI-2 were present in *in vitro* cultures of both *P. aeruginosa* and the host microflora, indicating that the

host's own bacteria might be stimulating the growth of *P. aeruginosa* (Duan et al, 2003).

Conclusion:

Since many important animal pathogens use quorum-sensing to regulate virulence, strategies intended to interfere with their signalling systems, will likely have many potential applications. The disruption of signalling systems offers an opportunity to prevent the bacteria from responding to the signal and thereby prevent the expression of virulence factors. Biotechnological research is now focused on the development of AHL antagonists. In medicine, such molecules have a potential use as antimicrobial drugs. In biotechnology, quorum sensing could be used to control fermentation processes either by triggering early production of a desired metabolite or by making the onset of synthesis of a toxic product dependent on the addition of an exogenous AHL. Applications for quorum sensing are presently limited by our understanding of quorum-sensing mechanisms.

Although advances have been made in the use of quorum sensing, further understanding of quorum functionality is required before the power of this tool can be fully realised. So far we have been able to block quorum sensing and make use of isolated components for driving protein expression. However, the full-scale manipulation of the bacterial quorum circuit in a biotechnological application remains an unfulfilled goal. How can we use the wide-reaching and sensitive quorum circuit to tailor the full range of bacterial physiological phenomena to meet specific performance goals, such as bio-based computers or controllers? What aspects of prokaryotic-eukaryotic interaction are essential for bacterial infection or symbiotic relationships? What are the limits to bacterial group behaviour, and are there levels of amplitude for such behaviour that can be characterised and predicted from environmental conditions? These questions will require more basic scientific inquiry into quorum sensing and, equally importantly, more efforts in applying this basic knowledge.

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